

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE LEVEL OF COMPETENCE IN THE ACTIVITY OF A TEACHER

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Annotation. This article widely reveals the importance of the level of competence in pedagogical activity.

Key words: professional competence, personal competence, creative competence, information competence, teacher, lesson.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bugungi kun pedagog faoliyatida kompetentlik darajasining ahamiyati keng yotirilgan.

Kalit soʻzlari: kasbiy kompetentlik, shaxsiy kompetentlik, kreativ kompetentlik, informatsion kompetentlik, oʻqituvchi, dars.

Аннотация. В данной статье широко раскрыто значение уровня компетентности в педагогической деятельности.

Ключевые слова: профессиональная компетентность, личная компетентность, творческая компетентность, информационная компетентность, учитель, урок.

In the educational process, teachers should rationally and equitably use their position to foster in students such moral qualities as organization, diligence, and mutual respect. They should also foster mental qualities such as a conscious approach to learning and a sense of purpose in their activities. Additionally, they should encourage volitional qualities like attention control, behavior management, and self-control to help students overcome difficulties.

Regardless of how creatively a teacher attempts to organize a lesson, if students' cognitive engagement is not ensured and interaction is not established, deficiencies remain in the effort to educate a spiritually mature individual, a person at the appropriate level.

The state pays much attention to the professional development of teachers, and there is a growing demand for expanding the number of specialists in the highest category. One of the most significant challenges facing teachers today is their professional development, including mastering modern technologies. The characteristics of a modern schoolteacher, which are developed through their creative activities, grow and evolve primarily through practical work and the acquisition of pedagogical experience.

In today's society, the independent acquisition of knowledge and improvement of qualifications by teachers on the one hand demonstrates the successful development of pedagogical activities, and on the other, it is a significant task, as this process prevents intellectual stagnation.

As you are aware, the teaching profession is not open to all. Only those teachers who have a passion for the profession and are inclined towards the activity and possess the necessary qualifications can achieve success. We will discuss the level of teacher competence below.

Competence (from the Latin word "competere") refers to the ability to meet the requirements of an activity, as well as the suitability and legal capacity to perform it. In the context of professional development, professional competence is a key criterion for assessing a specialist's level of training and professional maturity.

In relation to the concept of professional competence, there are various approaches put forward by researchers. It is seen as a characteristic that describes the attitude of an individual towards specific requirements of a job or, more specifically, towards certain aspects of their work. For instance, E.F. Zeer, a researcher, examining the development of professional competence over time, found that as individuals reach professional maturity, various aspects of competence become integrated and the connection between them and professionally significant personal qualities increases.

In particular, the main aspects of professional competence include relevant training and experience, self-knowledge, self-assurance, the ability to correctly perceive shortcomings in others, and other personal qualities that contribute to professional maturity. An analysis of these points allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the professional competency of a teacher, which can be described as a combination of several specific aspects, including personal, social, creative, and methodological competencies.

Personal competence is characterized by several key factors, including social outlook, scientific and intellectual capacity, creativity, ability to effectively communicate with others, flexibility of thought, and the variety of approaches used in problem-solving. Additionally, it is important to consider the level of development of personal and professional attributes that meet the needs of a given occupation. Furthermore, an active lifestyle and civic engagement are significant aspects to consider.

Methodological competence implies knowledge, mastery, and practical application of methods, techniques, and tools for the efficient organization of

educational and management processes. It also encompasses the ability to evaluate the outcomes of professional activities, explore advanced pedagogical practices and international experiences, as well as plan and successfully execute educational programs.

Creative competence, or the ability to create, is the acquisition of skills in innovation, creativity, and organization. This competence plays a significant role not only in generating new ideas, but also in shaping a person's lifestyle and inner world.

Information competence refers to the level of development of skills required for independently searching, analyzing, selecting, processing, and transmitting relevant information related to both personal and professional endeavors, utilizing modern information and communication technologies. In these processes, the alignment of the teacher's personal orientation with the field of professional practice, the harmony between their personal abilities, professional knowledge, qualifications, skills, professional attributes, and work experience, and the successful integration of innovative practices into their field of work are identified as critical factors in the development of innovation competency.

The successful resolution of complex issues such as the education and upbringing of young people largely depends on the ideological convictions, professional skills, general knowledge, culture, and competence of teachers. A modern educator must be able to influence students, shape their desires, beliefs, interests, and opportunities. In essence, a modern educational institution requires a highly moral, active, and sought-after teacher-mentor.

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